

README file

A new class of diarylethene compounds that exhibit turn-on emission: From aggregation-induced emission to anti-Kasha emission

dimer: coordinates of extracted dimers of PO-DTE unit cell; .pdb files

monomer: optimised geometries of all monomers at S_0 and S_1 , and PO-DTE open and closed form with one water molecule

PES scan: individual input geometries for potential energy surface scan, coordinates